

<h2>D6.5</h2> <h3>Federated Trust and Identity (T&I) technical requirements, architecture and best practices</h3>										
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Abstract	Definition of T&I best practices to support new additional Diamond OA journal partners to support single sign-on, and definition of T&I OJP technical architecture and interoperability framework and standards.

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List of Acronyms

AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
AARC	Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration
BPA	Blueprint Architecture
Diamond OA	Diamond Open Access
DPCoCo	Data Protection Code of Conduct
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IAM	Identity and Access Management
ID	Identifier
IdP	Identity Provider
JWT	JSON Web Tokens
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OJP	Open Journal Platforms
OJS	Open Journal Systems
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PKCE	Proof Key for Code Exchange
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
REFEDS	Research and Education FEDerations group

RCIAM	Identity Access Management for Research Communities
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
Sirtfi	Security Incident Response Trust Framework for Federated Identity
SRCE	University of Zagreb University Computing Centre
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities
SSO	Single Sign-On
T&I	Trust & Identity
VO	Virtual Organisation
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
ZPID	Leibniz Institute for Psychology

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable **D6.5** defines what Open Journal Platforms (OJP) and Diamond Open Access (Diamond OA) partners must adopt to participate in a **federated Trust & Identity (T&I)** ecosystem: (i) **best practices to onboard new partners to Single Sign-On (SSO)**, and (ii) the **T&I technical architecture** together with the **interoperability framework and standards** that OJP should implement or align to. The report is **public** and part of **WP6: Journals' Data Reuse and Uptake in (European Open Science Cloud) EOSC**.

The document first states the **scope and objectives** of D6.5 and positions it within CRAFT-OA's technical work. It then sets out **technical requirements** for federated T&I in journal platforms, proposes a **reference architecture** showing the components and interfaces needed for SSO, and lists the **interoperability framework and standards** to ensure that platforms implement T&I consistently. Finally, it provides **best-practice guidance** to help **new Diamond OA partners** adopt SSO smoothly, alongside a **conformance checklist** that journals and platforms can use to verify that requirements, architecture elements, and standards are in place. Together, these elements fulfil the Grant Agreement's success criteria for D6.5.

The structure of the document is as follows:

- **Section 2:** Federated T&I technical architecture and requirements.
- **Section 3:** T&I technical architecture for Open Journal System (OJS), discusses the technical architecture for OJS, the pilots that have been identified, their requirements, implementation and results.
- **Section 4:** Evaluation.
- **Section 5:** Conclusions.

2 FEDERATED TRUST & IDENTITY (T&I) — TECHNICAL ARCHITECTURE AND REQUIREMENT

2.1 Why Authentication & Authorisation matter

Federated Authentication and Authorisation are foundational for enabling secure and seamless access to digital publishing services across institutions and countries.

In the context of Diamond Open Access (OA), editors, reviewers, and authors typically belong to different organisations, each operating its own identity management system. Without federated access, these users would need to maintain multiple local accounts, increasing administrative overhead and security risks.

Authentication verifies who the user is and ensures that the identity originates from a trusted source such as a home institution or Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID¹).

Authorisation determines what the authenticated user is allowed to do within a service, e.g. submit a manuscript, perform peer review, or manage editorial workflows.

Together they enable:

- **Single Sign-On (SSO)** – one secure login reused across multiple services.
- **Improved security** – delegated authentication through trusted identity providers (IdP).
- **Traceability and auditability** – essential for accountability in editorial processes.
- **User convenience and scalability** – lowering barriers to participation for distributed communities.

These capabilities align with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and Open Science principles by allowing verified, privacy-preserving access to interoperable research infrastructures.

2.2 Challenges & Consideration for Social Science and Humanities

The Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) community relies on a highly diverse ecosystem of institutions, repositories, and journals. Several challenges arise when introducing federated identity management:

- **Fragmented identity landscape:** many organisations operate isolated user databases that are not connected to academic federations.

¹ <https://orcid.org/>

- **Heterogeneous attributes and semantics:** editorial and reviewer roles vary across systems, complicating authorisation.
- **Privacy and consent:** personal information and sensitive data require transparent consent flows and strict General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance.
- **Limited resources:** small publishers often lack technical capacity to deploy and maintain their own Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI).
- **User experience:** researchers expect low-friction login using familiar credentials such as ORCID or institutional accounts.
- **Assurance and governance:** local identity assurance levels must map to federated trust policies.

The federated T&I model proposed in CRAFT-OA mitigates these issues through an SSO solution built on existing academic and community federations, requiring no local Identity Provider operation.

2.3 EOSC AAI architecture

The [EOSC AAI Architecture 2025](#) defines the architectural and technical framework for the initial implementation of the EOSC AAI Federation within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

It provides practical guidance for candidate EOSC Nodes that wish to interconnect their Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructures (AAIs) under a shared policy and trust model, enabling secure interoperability and SSO across the EOSC ecosystem.

2.3.1 EOSC Nodes and their role

In EOSC, a Node acts as the organisational and technical integration point through which services join the EOSC AAI Federation. Nodes enrol once they satisfy the defined technical and policy requirements; every service is therefore onboarded through a Node, not directly to the Federation. This approach ensures accountability, consistent policy application, and scalability as more Nodes join over time.

The long-term vision is a *full-mesh, dynamic topology* where Nodes can establish direct trust relationships. However, until OpenID Federation² and related tooling are mature enough to support that model, the initial implementation uses a *hub-and-spoke topology*, which is practical today while remaining compatible with future evolution.

The design follows three principles:

- Minimal baseline of requirements;
- Simplicity of component setup;

² https://openid.net/specs/openid-federation-1_0.html

- Feasibility with current technology.

2.3.2 Core architectural components

The EOSC AAI Federation comprises a set of well-defined components that perform a specific role within the overall trust and identity framework:

- **Infrastructure Proxy** – the mandatory gateway each Node operates to broker authentication and authorisation for its services.
- **Community AAI / Collaboration Platform** – an optional component that manages community-specific groups, roles, and membership information.
- **Unified Identity Layer** – an optional configuration in which a Node adopts the common Identity Layer provided by the Federation’s Central Hub.

A Central Hub provides the Trust and Identity Layer, aggregating trust anchors and metadata from all registered Nodes. This arrangement establishes transitive trust: each Node connects once to the Hub and thereby gains trust with every other registered Node.

2.3.3 rds

The EOSC AAI Federation is based on the Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration (AARC) Blueprint Architecture³ (BPA) and leverages mature, standards-based protocols and profiles that guarantee secure and consistent interactions among Nodes.

2.3.3.1 CORE PROTOCOLS

- OpenID Connect (OIDC)⁴ and OAuth 2.0⁵ – the primary protocols for SSO and authorisation.
- Security Assertion Markup Language (SAML) 2.0⁶ – legacy but maintained for backward compatibility with existing identity federations.
- OpenID Federation 1.0⁷ – foreseen for future, dynamic metadata and trust-management capabilities.

2.3.3.2 EOSC NODE FEDERATED AAI REQUIREMENTS

Each Node participating in the Federation must operate at least one Infrastructure Proxy implementing the AARC BPA and may operate one or more Community AAIs / Collaboration Platforms.

³ <https://aarc-community.org/architecture/>

⁴ <https://openid.net/developers/how-connect-works/>

⁵ <https://oauth.net/2/>

⁶ <https://www.oasis-open.org/standard/saml/>

⁷ <https://openid.net/specs/openid-federation-1.0.html>

All components must be registered in the EOSC AAI Federation Registry, which stores Node details, metadata, supported protocols, and compliance information.

Functionally:

- The Infrastructure Proxy acts as the Node’s trusted interface with the Hub, supporting OIDC, OAuth 2.0 Token Introspection ([RFC 7662](#)), and OAuth 2.0 Proxied Token Introspection ([AARC-G052](#)).
- Both Infrastructure Proxies and Community AAls must process and express group membership and role information per [AARC-G069](#).
- Proof Key for Code Exchange ([PKCE](#)) and nonce parameters must be used for authorisation-code flows, and insecure flows (such as the Implicit Grant) must be prohibited.
- All interactions must comply with the Federation’s security and privacy policy framework.

2.3.3.3 INFORMATION (CLAIMS) AVAILABLE IN THE EOSC AAI FEDERATION

Nodes exchange a common set of user information (claims in the OpenID/OAuth terminology) to support consistent identity and authorisation across the Federation.

The table below summarises the expected information elements and their technical names.

Type of information	Technical name (claim)	Purpose / use
Persistent user identifier	sub / voperson_id	Stable, non-reassignable identifier for the user
Name	name, given_name, family_name	Human-readable identity for display and communication
Email address	email	Enables contact and notifications where required
Organisational details	voperson_external_affiliation, schacHomeOrganization	Indicates the user’s home organisation and scoped affiliation
Community group memberships & roles	entitlements	Expresses group memberships, roles or rights defined by communities or projects
Identity assurance	eduperson_assurance	Conveys the level of identity proofing and credential management associated with the user’s identity, as defined in the (Research and Education FEDerations group (REFEDS) Assurance Framework)

Table 1: User information elements (claims) available in the EOSC AAI Federation

2.3.3.4 SECURITY AND COMPLIANCE BASELINE

All Nodes participating in the Federation must implement a shared security and incident-response baseline that includes:

- Security Incident Response Trust Framework for Federated Identity ([Sirtfi](#)⁸);
- Security Operational Baseline ([AARC-G084](#)⁹) – common procedures for secure infrastructure operation;
- Research and Education FEDerations group (REFEDS) Data Protection Code of Conduct v2 ([DPCoCo](#)¹⁰) – or another GDPR-aligned data protection framework.

These measures ensure consistent privacy protection, operational security, and incident-response coordination across all Nodes and services within the Federation.

2.4 EGI Check-In Single Sign-On

The [EGI Check-in service](#)¹¹ provides a comprehensive set of Identity and Access Management (IAM) components that enable users to access services and resources securely. It functions as an intermediary between users, IdPs, and services, managing authentication and authorisation to deliver a seamless SSO experience across federated environments. Check-in is aligned and technically compatible with the EOSC AAI Architecture 2025¹², implementing the interfaces, profiles, and trust model foreseen for both Infrastructure Proxies and Community AAls.

Check-in builds on the Identity Access Management for Research Communities ([RCIAM](#))¹³ solution, a suite of open-source IAM tools designed in accordance with the AARC¹⁴ BPA. RCIAM includes:

- a multi-protocol Service Proxy (based on [Keycloak](#)¹⁵) supporting OAuth 2.0, OIDC, and SAML 2.0;
- a [Keycloak extension for group-management](#)¹⁶ enabling fine-grained authorisation; and
- a service-management portal for onboarding and administering services, based on the [RCIAM Federation Registry](#)¹⁷.

⁸ <https://refeds.org/sirtfi>

⁹ <https://aarc-community.org/guidelines/aarc-g084/>

¹⁰ <https://wiki.refeds.org/display/CODE/Data+Protection+Code+of+Conduct+Home>

¹¹ <https://www.egi.eu/service/check-in/>

¹² <https://zenodo.org/records/15388270>

¹³ <https://rciam.github.io/rciam-docs/>

¹⁴ <https://aarc-community.org/about/>

¹⁵ <https://github.com/eosc-kc/keycloak>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/rciam/keycloak-group-management>

¹⁷ <https://federation.rciam.grnet.gr/docs/>

This foundation provides Check-in with a modular and extensible architecture that supports both infrastructure-level integration and community-level authorisation management, ensuring long-term compatibility with the evolving EOSC AAI Federation model.

2.4.1 Supported authentication and authorisation standards

EGI Check-in supports the main standards and guidelines referenced in the EOSC AAI Architecture 2025, ensuring interoperability with other federated identity and access systems.

Its implementation is based on:

- OIDC and OAuth 2.0, for web- and API-based authentication and authorisation; and
- SAML 2.0, providing backward compatibility with existing research and education federations through eduGAIN, and supporting legacy services that cannot yet adopt OIDC.

Check-in follows the AARC BPA, translating authentication assertions and releasing harmonised user attributes in accordance with the AARC Profile ([AARC-G056](#)¹⁸) and the user claims available in the EOSC AAI Federation, which are outlined in [Section 3.3.3.3](#).

It also supports token-based authorisation, including OAuth 2.0 Token Introspection ([RFC 7662](#)¹⁹) and OAuth 2.0 Proxied Token Introspection ([AARC-G052](#)²⁰), enabling secure validation of tokens issued by trusted authorisation servers.

Furthermore, EGI Check-in is already OpenID Federation-ready, implementing the metadata-discovery and trust-establishment mechanisms required for the next phase of the EOSC AAI Federation. This will enable its integration into the evolving federation topology once OpenID Federation is adopted across EOSC Nodes.

2.4.2 Identity Management

EGI Check-in implements an Identity Management layer which allows users to associate multiple credentials—such as institutional, ORCID, or social identities—into a single, persistent digital identity.

This ensures that users are recognised consistently across integrated services even when using different IdPs.

¹⁸ <https://aarc-community.org/guidelines/aarc-g056/>

¹⁹ <https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/rfc7662>

²⁰ <https://aarc-community.org/guidelines/aarc-g052/>

2.4.3 Collaboration Management

In addition to acting as an Infrastructure Proxy, Check-in also provides Community AAI or Collaboration Management functionality through its integrated Virtual Organisation (VO) management system.

VOs represent communities or projects whose members require access to shared services.

Check-in offers tools to:

- Define VO membership policies and organisational structures.
- Assign groups and roles following the [AARC-G069](#)²¹ Guidelines for Group and Role Expression.
- Expose these authorisation attributes as standard OIDC²² claims or SAML assertions to relying services.

This supports fine-grained, role-based access control, allowing applications, such as publishing platforms, to authorise users based on their federated community roles rather than local accounts.

2.5 Proof of Concepts: how OJS can integrate with SSO

A proof of concept has been implemented to demonstrate how a publishing platform—specifically Open Journal Systems (OJS)—can be integrated into the EOSC AAI Federation using an EOSC AAI compatible solution such as EGI Check-in.

The scenario shows how federated SSO enables secure and seamless access for authors, editors, reviewers and administrators in Diamond OA workflows.

1. In this setup, the OJS instance is configured as an OIDC client, acting as a Service Provider that trusts the EGI Check-in Infrastructure Proxy.
2. When a user attempts to access the journal, OJS redirects the user to the proxy to select their preferred upstream IdP for authentication.
3. After successful login, the proxy issues an Identifier (ID) token and a set of user claims (such as identifier, name, email, affiliation, group membership, and roles) through the OIDC UserInfo endpoint.
4. OJS maps these federated attributes to its internal role model—author, editor, reviewer—and grants access accordingly.
5. The same SSO flow also manages attribute filtering, session lifetime, logout, and, where necessary, fallback to local accounts.
6. Integrated logging mechanisms record user activity, providing auditability and ensuring that access can be securely revoked when required.

²¹ <https://aarc-community.org/guidelines/aarc-g069/>

²² <https://openid.net/developers/how-connect-works/>

The sequence of interactions between the user, OJS, and EGI Check-in is illustrated in Figure 1, which shows the redirection-based authentication flow and the exchange of user information between components.

Figure 1: Federated Single Sign-On flow between OJS and EGI Check-in

This proof of concept confirms the technical viability of connecting publishing platforms to a federated AAI ecosystem aligned with the EOSC AAI Architecture 2025.

3 T&I TECHNICAL ARCHITECTURE FOR OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEM (OJS)

3.1 SRCE pilot

3.1.1 Overview

The University of Zagreb University Computing Centre (SRCE) pilot focused on integrating OJS with the EGI Check-in service to enable federated SSO in alignment with the EOSC AAI Architecture. The objective was to demonstrate that a multi-journal OJS installation can adopt OIDC-based federated login through an EOSC AAI-compatible Infrastructure Proxy, thereby simplifying user onboarding and reducing administrative overhead.

Initially, the pilot used the [OJS OpenID plugin developed by the Leibniz Institute for Psychology \(ZPID\)](#)²³, which required extensive configuration changes to operate with recent OJS releases. Subsequently, SRCE migrated to the Public Knowledge Project ([PKP](#))–[maintained OpenID plugin repository](#)²⁴, which introduced fixes and improvements based on issues identified through SRCE’s testing and feedback.

This iterative process helped validate OIDC support for OJS and informed upstream development to strengthen the plugin’s interoperability with OpenID Providers in accordance with the EOSC AAI Architecture.

3.1.2 Requirements

The pilot implementation was designed to meet the following requirements:

- **Federated authentication** for authors, editors, and reviewers using their institutional, or other federated credentials (e.g. ORCID) through EGI Check-in.
- **Standards compliance**, ensuring conformance with OIDC and OAuth 2.0 as specified in the AARC/EOSC AAI interoperability guidelines.
- **Seamless user onboarding**, allowing account creation from federated identities without requiring local passwords.
- **Attribute mapping** from Check-in user claims (persistent user identifier, name, email) to OJS user records.
- **Secure configuration**, including validation of OIDC redirect Uniform Resource Identifiers (URI), session management, and logout handling across multiple journals.

²³ <https://github.com/leibniz-psychology/openid>

²⁴ <https://github.com/pkp/openid>

- **Scalability**, enabling support for multi-journal OJS installations via a shared OIDC configuration.

3.1.3 Implementation

SRCE deployed a test OJS 3.4.0.7 instance and integrated it with the EGI Check-in demo environment²⁵. The OJS service was registered as an OIDC client via the [EGI Check-in Federation Registry](#). Registration included defining the client credentials (client id ojs-demo), declaring redirect and logout URIs, selecting requested scopes, and linking the client with SRCE as the responsible service provider organisation. This configuration allowed integration between the test OJS instance and the demo integration environment of EGI Check-in.

Figure 2 shows the general service registration metadata, including the service name (Demo OJS), description, organisation details, and integration environment.

²⁵ <https://aai-demo.egi.eu/>

Service was registered at: 2024/10/10 19:59:25

General Protocol Specific

Service name * Demo OJS
Human-readable application name. (This information will be shown in the Consent Page)

Integration * Demo +
Environment

Logo https://hrcak.srce.hr/javno/assets/images/hrcak-logo.png
URL that points to a logo image. (Logo will be displayed in the Consent Page)

Service Website URL https://
Website URL for information about the service (This information will be shown in the Consent Page)

Description * Demo integration with OJS
Human-readable text description, plain text format (max 1000 characters) (This information will be shown in the Consent Page)

Select country * Croatia

Organisation * SRCE
Search for your organisation

Organisation * https://www.srce.unizg.hr
Website URL Link to the organization's website

Figure 2: OJS service registration in the EGI Check-in Federation Registry: General metadata view

Figure 3 illustrates the protocol-specific configuration, highlighting the OIDC parameters used for the pilot (client ID, authorisation code flow, allowed scopes, and login/logout redirect URIs).

Service was registered at: 2024/10/10 19:59:25

General Protocol Specific

Select Protocol *

Client ID
Unique identifier. If you leave this blank it will be automatically generated.

Application Type * Web Native
Kind of the application. Web Clients MUST only register URLs using the https scheme as redirect_uris; they MAY use the http scheme when using localhost as the hostname. Native Clients MUST only register redirect_uris using custom URI schemes or URLs using the http scheme with localhost as the hostname.

Grant Types authorization code
 client credentials
 token-exchange
 device code
 implicit (deprecated)

Token Endpoint * Client Secret over HTTP Basic
 Authorization Method Client Secret over HTTP POST
 Client Secret via symmetrically-signed JWT assertion
 Asymmetrically-signed JWT assertion
 No authentication

Client Secret * Display client secret:

Introspection Allow calls to the Introspection Endpoint?
Access to the Token Introspection endpoint is restricted to confidential clients.

Scope *	
openid	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
voperson_id	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
email	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
profile	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
voperson_external_affiliation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
schac_home_organization	<input type="checkbox"/>
aarc	<input type="checkbox"/>
entitlements	<input type="checkbox"/>
offline_access	<input type="checkbox"/>
orcid	<input type="checkbox"/>
eduperson_entitlement	<input type="checkbox"/>

Redirect URI(s) *
URIs that the client can be redirected to. Different URI validation rules apply depending on the application type.

Post Logout Redirect URI(s)
URLs to request that the End-User's browser be redirected after a logout has been performed using the post_logout_redirect_uri parameter.

Figure 3: OJS service registration in the EGI Check-in Federation Registry: Protocol-specific configuration

Early testing of the ZPID OpenID plugin (v3.2.1 / v3.3.0.7) showed partial compatibility: authentication worked after manual configuration but required additional adjustments to support OJS v3.4.

SRCE then transitioned to the PKP-maintained OIDC plugin repository, which introduced fixes and improvements based on issues identified through SRCE's testing and feedback. SRCE

actively collaborated with PKP developers through the public GitHub repository issues²⁶ and the PKP community forum, contributing test results, issue reports, and feature requests. Key enhancements implemented in the PKP plugin included:

- synchronisation of user data using claims available through the OIDC UserInfo endpoint, such as `given_name`, `family_name`, and `email`; and
- fixes to login and post-logout redirect URI handling for multi-journal OJS installations.

The OJS Plugin for OpenID integration (<https://github.com/pkp/openid>) was developed to address the absence of OpenID authentication and SSO functionality in the OJS. The development of this plugin was based on the OAuth plugin²⁷, which already included core authentication features such as obtaining an authentication code and handling JSON Web Tokens (JWT). Main features of the plugin relevant for this pilot:

- OpenID Authentication: the plugin replaces the standard OJS login with authentication through an OpenID provider.
- Automatic User Registration: users who log in via an OpenID provider are automatically added to the OJS database, along with user data delivered from the provider (OpenID identifier, email, given name, family name). Users created in this way are not assigned any roles by default. After a successful login, they can select a role for a specific journal in their profile - such as author, reader, or reviewer. Additional roles may be assigned by the journal manager or the OJS administrator.
- Account Linking: if OJS already contains local user accounts, these existing accounts can be connected to the newly created OpenID-based accounts during the first OpenID login, without the possibility of further using local OJS authentication ensuring smooth *migration* to different ways of authentication.

²⁶ <https://github.com/pkp/openid/issues>

²⁷ <https://github.com/ulsdevteam/pkp-oauth>

Figure 4: OJS sign in form, local accounts supported + EGI

Figure 5: EGI identity provider list; search for additional

Figure 6: Connecting existing OJS account with the one from identity provider

Figure 7: For new OJS accounts user data is requested

Figure 8: Registration completed

A local Apache `mod_auth_openidc` configuration was also tested as an alternative to the plugin-based approach. While authentication through EGI Check-in completed successfully, the session was not maintained after login, preventing authenticated access to OJS. This confirmed that the native OJS OIDC plugin provides a more reliable and maintainable solution for long-term integration.

3.1.4 Results

The final pilot configuration achieved reliable SSO between OJS—acting as an OIDC client—and EGI Check-in, functioning as an EOSC AAI-compatible OpenID Provider. Users could authenticate using their institutional credentials, and OJS automatically created local accounts populated with federated attributes — namely the persistent user identifier, name, and email. This enabled seamless onboarding for new contributors and editors without local credentials, while maintaining compatibility with the existing OJS role model.

Observed limitations, such as the handling of redirect URIs for multi-journal installations, were resolved, confirming that OJS can now handle multiple journals using shared login/logout redirect URIs under a single OIDC client registration.

Group and role mapping from federated attributes is not yet supported by the current OJS OIDC plugin. As a result, editorial permissions must still be managed within OJS, while the plugin currently provides only federated login/logout and attribute population. In OJS, the administrator typically assigns a user the Journal Manager role, after which the Journal Manager is responsible for managing other users and assigning roles within their journal. Both the administrator and the Journal Manager can create, edit, and remove roles, but the Journal Manager's scope is limited to their own journal. Although the administrator technically has the ability to modify roles and permissions, this is generally unnecessary, as role and permission management is delegated to Journal Managers.

Overall, the SRCE pilot validated that OJS can connect as an OIDC client to an EOSC AAI-compatible Infrastructure Proxy, contributing to upstream OIDC plugin improvements and providing a reusable reference for future OJS OpenID plugin deployments.

3.2 Masaryk University pilot

3.2.1 Overview

The Masaryk University pilot, conducted in addition to the SRCE pilot, focused on integrating OJS with the EGI Check-in service to enable federated SSO in alignment with the EOSC AAI Architecture. The objective was to test the compatibility of different OJS versions and the corresponding authentication plugin, as well as to demonstrate that both multi-journal and single-journal OJS installations can adopt OIDC-based federated login through an EOSC AAI-compatible Infrastructure Proxy, thereby simplifying user onboarding and reducing administrative overhead.

Building on the experience gained from the previous SRCE pilot, the implementation at Masaryk University used exclusively the [OpenID authentication plugin](#)²⁸ maintained by the PKP group.

During the process, several issues were identified and subsequently resolved. It was pointed out that the service must be properly configured to ensure correct operation. Throughout the pilot, several possible implementation scenarios were described and analysed.

3.2.2 Requirements

Similar to the SRCE pilot, the Masaryk University implementation aimed to achieve the same set of objectives and compliance requirements. An additional requirement for the multi-journal system was to preserve the legacy login and registration functionality alongside the federated authentication:

- **Federated authentication** for authors, editors, and reviewers using their institutional or other federated credentials (e.g. ORCID) through EGI Check-in.
- **Standards compliance**, ensuring conformance with OIDC and OAuth 2.0 as specified in the AARC/EOSC AAI interoperability guidelines.
- **Seamless user onboarding**, allowing account creation from federated identities without requiring local passwords.
- **Attribute mapping** from Check-in user claims (persistent user identifier, name, email) to OJS user records.
- **Secure configuration**, including validation of OIDC redirect URIs, session management, and logout handling across multiple journals.

²⁸ <https://github.com/pkp/openid>

- **Scalability**, enabling support for multi-journal OJS installations via a shared OIDC configuration.
- **Legacy login and registration**, maintaining the original local login and user registration mechanism to allow access and onboarding for users who do not actively use any institutional or federated IdPs. This feature ensures inclusivity for independent researchers, external collaborators, and other contributors who rely solely on local OJS accounts, while also serving as a fallback option in case of temporary unavailability of the federated authentication service.

3.2.3 Implementation

Masaryk University implemented the authentication plugin on three independent OJS installations, each of which was separately integrated with the EGI Check-in demo environment. In all cases, the OJS services were configured as OIDC clients via the EGI Check-in Federation Registry. The configuration parameters for each service differed in client identifiers, redirect URIs, and logout URIs. All OJS installations used the `restful_url` configuration, which was properly reflected in the service setup within the Federation Registry.

Masaryk University was registered as the responsible Service Provider organisation within the Federation Registry, and all related service descriptions clearly indicated that the deployments represented test services operating in the demo mode.

Figure 9: the overview of all configured services corresponding to the individual OJS instances within the EGI Check-in Federation Registry under the Manage Services section.

The plugin was installed in each instance directly from the **Plugin Gallery**, ensuring that the plugin version matched the installed OJS version and was up to date.

Figure 10: plugin installation window for OJS 3.4.0.

3.2.3.1 DIFFERENT SETUPS

For each OJS installation, a separate service entry had to be created within the **EGI Check-in Federation Registry**. As a result, part of the configuration is specific to each individual service, while certain settings remain the same across all instances.

Common settings across all instances:

- **Integration Environment:** Demo
- **Selected country:** Czech Republic
- **Organisation:** Masaryk University
- **Organisation Website URL:** <http://www.muni.cz/>
- **Selected Protocol:** OIDC Service
- **Application Type:** Web

The screenshot displays the configuration interface for a registered service in the EGI Check-in Federation Registry. The 'General' tab is active, and the 'Protocol Specific' section is expanded for 'OIDC Service'. Key configuration elements include:

- Select Protocol:** OIDC Service
- Client ID:** ojs3-3-demo (Unique identifier, automatically generated if blank)
- Application Type:** Web (selected over Native)
- Grant Types:** authorization code (selected), client credentials, token-exchange, device code, implicit (deprecated)
- Token Endpoint Authorization Method:** Client Secret over HTTP Basic (selected), Client Secret over HTTP POST, Client Secret via symmetrically-signed JWT assertion, Asymmetrically-signed JWT assertion, No authentication
- Client Secret:** Display client secret (unchecked), with a masked input field
- Introspection:** Allow calls to the Introspection Endpoint? (checked)
- Scope:** A table of scopes with checkboxes:

openid	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
voperson_id	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
email	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
profile	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
voperson_external_affiliation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
schac_home_organization	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
aarc	<input type="checkbox"/>
entitlements	<input type="checkbox"/>
offline_access	<input type="checkbox"/>
orcid	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
- Redirect URI(s):** https://summerschool2025.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/openid/doAuthentication?provider=custom
- Post Logout Redirect URI(s):** https://summerschool2025.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/index

Figure 11: figure illustrates an example configuration of one of the registered services within the EGI Check-in Federation Registry.

The plugin configuration within OJS differed between installations only in the login credentials, specifically the *Client ID* and *Client Secret* values. All other configuration parameters remained consistent across the tested OJS versions.

OpenID Authentication Plugin x

OpenId Provider:

Please enter the following information according to your OpenID provider.

Custom OpenID Provider

If you want to use a custom OpenID Connect Provider (e.g. a self-hosted Keycloak server), you have to provide the URL to the OpenID configuration endpoint and the client credentials. **https://summerschool2025.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/openid/doAuthentication?provider=custom**

Please enter the configuration URL of your OpenID provider. The URL must end with ".well-known/openid-configuration" (e.g. "https://sso.example.com/auth/realms/master/.well-known/openid-configuration").

Custom login button settings

Please enter a URL to an image (46x41) to be displayed on the login button. If no image is provided, the OpenID logo will be shown. *Please enter the label of the login button.*

Login credentials

Please enter your clientId. *Please enter your client secret.*

ORCID OpenID Connect

Google OpenID Connect

Microsoft Azure Active Directory

Apple ID

Advanced plugin functions

The following fields are optional. They are not required to connect to an OpenID provider.

Enable legacy login
Enable this option if you want users to be able to login with the application's login form in addition to the OpenID logon.

Enable legacy registration
Enable this option if you want users to be able to register with the application's register form in addition to the OpenID logon.

Disable "Account Connection"
If this journal is new and has no existing user accounts, you can check this box to disable the account linking function. In this case the user will only be asked for additional details required by this application when registering an account via an OpenID provider.

Enable OpenID provider user data synchronization
Some user information, such as the given name, family name and email address, is transferred from the OpenID Provider to this application. Enable this option to automatically save this user information to the user account. (recommended)
Prevent the following fields from being modified within this application:

Given name readonly
 Family name readonly
 Email readonly

Figure 12: the complete configuration of the **OpenID plugin** within the OJS interface.

3.2.3.1.1 OJS 3.3.0-21

The installation was also used earlier this year for demonstrations and workshops during the Summer School 2025 in Coimbra. This instance represents a **multi-journal installation**, where the EGI Check-in integration was configured and enabled only for a specific journal rather than for the entire OJS installation. This selective configuration allowed for isolated testing and validation of the authentication workflow without affecting other journals hosted on the same platform.

Specific EGI Check-in Federation Registry:

- **Service name:** OJS3-3 TEST service MUNI
- **Service Website URL:** <https://summerschool2025.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/>
- **Client ID:** ojs3-3-demo
- **Client Secret:** different for each of the services
- **Redirect URI(s):**
<https://summerschool2025.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/openid/doAuthentication?provider=custom> (the link cannot be used independently).
- **Post Logout Redirect URI(s):**
<https://summerschool2025.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/index>

OpenID Authentication Plugin:

For this OJS instance, the released **tag v3_4_1-0**²⁹ of the *OpenID Authentication Plugin* was used, which is officially intended for OJS, OMP, and OPS versions 3.3.0.

After the installation and configuration of the plugin, an HTTP 500 error occurred during the registration attempt on the OJS side:

```
PHP Fatal error: Uncaught Error: Class "Firebase\JWT\Key" not found in [ojs_base]/plugins/generic/openid/handler/OpenIDHandler.inc.php:391
```

The error indicated the absence of the class *Firebase\JWT\Key*, which is not available in OJS version 3.3.x and was introduced in version 3.4.x. To resolve the issue, it was necessary to modify line 391 in the file *plugins/generic/openid/handler/OpenIDHandler.inc.php*.

The correction was made based on a similar code structure used in the OJS core file *pages/oa/oaHandler.inc.php*.

Original line: `$jwtPayload = JWT::decode($t, new \Firebase\JWT\Key($publicKey, 'RS256'));`
Corrected line: `$jwtPayload = JWT::decode($t, $publicKey, array('RS256'));`

After this modification, the plugin worked correctly for both user registration and login.

²⁹ https://github.com/pkp/openid/releases/tag/v3_4_1-0

The issue will be reported to the plugin maintainers via the **GitHub Issue Tracker**, including a proposed fix to ensure compatibility with OJS 3.3.x installations.

3.2.3.1.2 OJS 3.4.0-9

The instance represents a **single-journal OJS installation** and its configuration for **EGI Check-in integration**.

Specific EGI Check-in Federation Registry:

- **Service name:** OJS3-4 TEST service MUNI
- **Service Website URL:** <https://ojs3-4.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/>
- **Client ID:** ojs3-4-demo
- **Client Secret:** different for each of the services
- **Redirect URI(s):**
<https://ojs3-4.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/openid/doAuthentication?provider=custom>
(the link cannot be used independently).
- **Post Logout Redirect URI(s):**
<https://ojs3-4.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/index>

OpenID Authentication Plugin:

For this OJS instance, the released **tag v4_1_0-0**³⁰ of the *OpenID Authentication Plugin* was used, which is officially intended for OJS, OMP, and OPS versions 3.4.0.

3.2.3.1.3 OJS 3.5.0-1: Multi-journal system, single journal setup

The instance represents a **multi-journal OJS installation** with the plugin configured separately for each journal. The configuration shown corresponds to the current setup for **OJS version 3.5.0**.

Specific EGI Check-in Federation Registry:

- **Service name:** OJS3-5 TEST service MUNI
- **Service Website URL:** <https://ojs3-5.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/>
- **Client ID:** ojs3-5-demo
- **Client Secret:** different for each of the services
- **Redirect URI(s):**
<https://ojs3-5.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/openid/doAuthentication?provider=custom>
(the link cannot be used independently).
- **Post Logout Redirect URI(s):**
<https://ojs3-5.craft-oa.muni.cz/egi-test/index>

³⁰ https://github.com/pkp/openid/releases/tag/v4_1_0-0

OpenID Authentication Plugin:

For this OJS instance, the released **tag v5_1_0-0**³¹ of the *OpenID Authentication Plugin* was used, which is officially intended for OJS, OMP, and OPS versions 3.5.0.

3.2.3.1.4 OJS 3.5.0-1: Multi-journal system, multi-journal setup

The instance represents a **multi-journal OJS installation** with the plugin configured at the **administrator level** for all journals within the installation. In this configuration, individual journals cannot modify or disable the plugin. Its use is therefore mandatory for all journals in the given installation and is fully governed by the system administrator's settings.

Currently, this configuration option is **not active** in the installation, and the **single-journal setup** described above is being used instead. The multi-journal variant was only configured within the **EGI Check-in service settings** and tested accordingly. Since this is a **test instance**, the plugin has been enabled only for a specific journal.

Specific EGI Check-in Federation Registry:

- **Service name:** OJS3-5 TEST service MUNI - multi-journal installation
- **Service Website URL:** <https://ojs3-5.craft-oa.muni.cz/>
- **Client ID:** ojs3-5-demo-multi
- **Client Secret:** different for each of the services
- **Redirect URI(s):**
<https://ojs3-5.craft-oa.muni.cz/index/openid/doAuthentication?provider=custom>
(the link cannot be used independently).
- **Post Logout Redirect URI(s):**
<https://ojs3-5.craft-oa.muni.cz/index>

OpenID Authentication Plugin:

For this OJS instance, the released **tag v5_1_0-0** of the *OpenID Authentication Plugin* was used, which is officially intended for OJS, OMP, and OPS versions 3.5.0.

3.2.3.2 PROCESS DESCRIPTION AFTER TESTING

Testing was conducted in the same way across all installations and is therefore described only once as a **shared test procedure**. The main implementation requirement in our specific case was to **preserve the original registration and login options**, allowing users to access the system **without using institutional authentication** through the EGI Check-in service.

During the configuration and testing phases, several issues were encountered that caused unexpected behaviour. Each of these issues was subsequently resolved and is described in detail below.

³¹ https://github.com/pkp/openid/releases/tag/v5_1_0-0

EGI testing journal

Current Archives About ▾

Search

Home / Sign in or register

Sign in or register

Sign in with your account at EGI testing journal

Username *

admin

Password *

[Forgot your password?](#)

Keep me logged in

Login

Sign in or register with:

EGI Check-in

Register Account (without Oauth)

Figure 13: OJS login page with EGI Check-in button and legacy local registration possibility.

3.2.3.2.1 Registration/login process with EGI Check-in service

1. Choosing IdP (figure 14.) - *EGI Check-in (Demo)* chosen
2. Choosing Institutional Login (figure 15.) - *Masaryk University* chosen
3. Masaryk University Unified Login (figure 16.)
 - a. Masaryk University Multi-factor authentication (figure 17.)
4. Email verification (figure 18., figure 19.)
 - a. problem with email greylist and link expiration time (figure 20.)
5. Grant Access to specific service after successful login (figure 21.)
6. The users determine whether they have an existing account or not (figure 22.)
 - a. Users don't have existing accounts and need to register (figure 23.)
 - b. Users have existing accounts, but forgot about it (figure 24.)
 - c. Users have existing accounts (figure 25.)
7. Registration complete (figure 26.)

After completing the entire process and either creating a new account or linking their institutional login to an existing one, the user can be managed in OJS as a standard user, with all functions operating without issues. The EGI Check-in integration extends the available options for registration, login, and logout, but it does not interfere with role management or regular operations within OJS. Therefore, the plugin and authentication through the EGI Check-in service **enhance the user experience** while imposing **no limitations on standard OJS functionality**.

Figure 14: Page for Choosing Identity Provider.

Figure 15: Page for Choosing Institutional Login.

Figure 16: Masaryk University Unified Login.

Figure 17: Masaryk University Multi-Factor authentication.

3.2.3.2.2 Greylist spam filtering problem

During the first login process via the **EGI Check-in service**, users are required to confirm their email address. A verification message is sent to the provided email address containing a confirmation link with a limited validity period.

During testing, the link's expiration time was set to **only 5 minutes**. However, due to greylist spam filtering, the verification email was repeatedly delivered **after the link had already expired**. The following figures illustrate the situation where the email could not be confirmed in time, preventing users from completing the login process and registering their accounts.

This issue was resolved by **increasing the verification link expiration time to 15 minutes**, after which the registration process proceeded correctly without further complications.

Figure 18: Email verification page.

Figure 19: Verification email.

Figure 20: Page with information about expired Action.

After attempting to verify an expired link, the user is redirected back to the original login page, where in most cases the login session has already expired as well. The page itself loaded correctly, but it was necessary to refresh it without cache and restart the entire login process, which consistently led to the same result.

Figure 21: Granting Access after successful login.

Figure 22: OJS Page where users can determine if they have or not the existing account.

Do you already have an account with EGI testing journal?

[Yes, I already have an account.](#)

[No, I'm new to EGI testing journal.](#)

Additional information is required to register to EGI testing journal:

Given Name *

Family Name *

Email *

Username *

Affiliation *

Country *

Yes, I agree to have my data collected and stored according to the [privacy statement](#). *

Yes, I would like to be notified of new publications and announcements.

Yes, I would like to be contacted with requests to review submissions to this journal.

Figure 23: New account registration.

[Home](#) / [Complete registration](#)

Do you already have an account with EGI testing journal?

[Yes, I already have an account.](#)

[No, I'm new to EGI testing journal.](#)

Additional information is required to register to EGI testing journal:

Errors occurred processing this form:

- The email address you provided already exists. Please try to log in to the existing account.

Given Name *

Family Name *

Figure 24: Trying to register an account with an already registered email address.

Do you already have an account with EGI testing journal?

[Yes, I already have an account.](#)

[No, I'm new to EGI testing journal.](#)

Please login to your account at EGI testing journal.
Your information will be updated automatically.

Username or email *

Password *

 [Forgot your password?](#)

[Login and connect accounts](#)

Figure 25: Connecting with existing account.

Registration complete

Thanks for registering! What would you like to do next?

- [View Submissions](#)
- [Make a New Submission](#)
- [Edit My Profile](#)
- [Continue Browsing](#)

Figure 26: Registration complete.

3.2.3.2.3 Logout Redirect URI problem

During the testing phase, the **logout functionality** was also evaluated. Since the **Post Logout Redirect URI(s)** parameter is not mandatory, the logout process was initially tested without it. In this case, the logout did not work correctly, and the system displayed the message **“Invalid redirect URI.”**

After configuring the service with a legitimate redirect address `https://ojs3-4.craft-
oa.muni.cz/egi-test/index/`, the same error message continued to appear. The issue was resolved
by correcting the redirect URI to remove the trailing slash. The properly configured address
is: `https://ojs3-4.craft-
oa.muni.cz/egi-test/index`

With this corrected address, the logout process functions properly and completes without
any issues.

Figure 27: Invalid redirect uri for account logout.

3.2.4 Results

The final pilot configuration confirmed that the OpenID plugin can be successfully configured and used—after resolving a few minor issues—across all **three currently supported OJS versions**. Both **multi-journal** and **single-journal** platforms were tested. On Masaryk University platforms, the integration with EGI Check-in did **not replace the existing local account creation and login options**, ensuring that users without institutional or federated credentials can still register and log in through the standard OJS mechanisms.

The final setup achieved reliable **SSO** between OJS—acting as an **OIDC client**—and **EGI Check-in**, functioning as an **EOSC AAI-compatible OpenID Provider**. Users were able to authenticate using their institutional credentials, with OJS automatically creating local accounts populated with federated attributes such as the **persistent user identifier, name, and email**. This ensured smooth onboarding for new contributors and editors without local credentials, while maintaining full compatibility with the OJS role and permission model and making login easier for those who already have an existing account.

A key finding of the pilot was that **successful authentication depends on a correctly configured service from the outset**. The integration was successfully tested against the **Masaryk University Unified Login** service, with **registration, login, and logout** processes all functioning as expected.

Issues identified during testing—such as redirect URI handling and verification link expiration—were resolved, confirming that OJS can reliably support multiple journals using shared or journal-specific configurations under a single OIDC client registration.

Overall, the **Masaryk University pilot** validated that OJS can effectively operate as an **OIDC client** integrated with an **EOSC AAI-compatible infrastructure** additionally to local account handling system, demonstrating both interoperability and flexibility across different OJS configurations and authentication scenarios.

4 EVALUATION

The evaluation of the pilots performed under CRAFT-OA Task 6.3 focused on assessing the technical feasibility, interoperability, and user-experience benefits of connecting Diamond OA journal platforms to a federated T&I ecosystem compatible with the EOSC AAI Architecture.

Both pilots (SRCE and Masaryk University) demonstrated that journal platforms such as OJS can integrate successfully with federated IAM solutions such as EGI Check-in, enabling secure, EOSC AAI-compatible SSO for distributed editorial workflows.

The pilots were evaluated against the following criteria:

Criterion	Description
Technical interoperability	Ability of OJS to establish SSO using OpenID Connect (OIDC) / OAuth 2.0; compliance with AARC Blueprint Architecture and EOSC AAI Architecture 2025 requirements
User experience	Seamlessness of login and onboarding for editors, reviewers, and authors using institutional or other trusted federated credentials, without requiring local account creation.
Security and privacy	Conformance with OAuth 2.0 security best practices, redirect-URI validation, logout handling, and GDPR-aligned data-release policies
Maintainability	Use of open-source components with active community support (e.g. PKP OpenID plugin, EGI Check-in Keycloak base) ensures sustainability and ease of upgrades.
Scalability and reusability	Feasibility of replicating the integration across multiple journals or platforms and its potential reuse in other Diamond OA contexts.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Findings:

- Interoperability and standards compliance: Both pilots confirmed that OJS can operate as a fully functional OIDC client within an EOSC-compatible federation. The use of EGI Check-in as the proxy ensured alignment with the AARC and EOSC AAI interoperability profiles.
- Multi-journal support—previously a technical limitation—was resolved through updates to the PKP OpenID plugin, allowing a single client registration to serve multi-journal OJS installations.
- User experience and onboarding: Federated SSO eliminated the need for local account creation. Users authenticated through institutional or other trusted federated credentials were recognised automatically, and local OJS accounts were created with pre-filled identity information (persistent identifier, name, email). This simplified onboarding for new editors and reviewers and reduced administrative overhead.
- Security and compliance: The pilots followed OAuth 2.0 security recommendations, validated redirect URIs, and avoided insecure flows. Logout propagation was tested successfully through Check-in's endpoints.
- Limitations: The current OJS OpenID plugin does not yet implement group or role mapping (e.g. based on AARC-G069 entitlements). Editorial permissions must therefore be managed within OJS.
- Maintainability and sustainability: The collaboration between SRCE and PKP resulted in upstream fixes, reducing the maintenance burden for future adopters. Both Check-in and the OJS plugin are open-source, ensuring sustainability through community support and alignment with EOSC AAI evolution.

Lessons learned and next steps:

- Federated authentication can be adopted by publishers with limited technical capacity, provided that reference configurations and documentation are made available.
- Future work should focus on extending OJS and the OpenID plugin to support federated group/role mapping, enabling attribute-based authorisation aligned with [AARC-G069](#).

The ongoing evolution of the EOSC AAI Federation toward OpenID Federation 1.0 will primarily affect the infrastructure-level trust establishment between proxies. For end-services such as OJS, this transition will be transparent, as they will continue to operate as standard OIDC clients while benefiting from a more scalable and automated federation model.

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